

Effect of Motivational Reward Practices on Principals Administration of Public Schools in Makurdi

Patricia Nguwasen Mando¹, Angelina Okewu Ogwuche², Doosuur Catherine Iyorchii³ and Emmanuel Msueorga Nyamngee⁴

^{1,2,3}Department of Educational Administration and Planning,

Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Educational Foundation, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Received 5 October 2024; Acceptance 25 October 2024; Published 31 October 2024.

Abstract

This study investigated the effects of motivational reward practices on principals' administration of public schools in Makurdi. The study employed descriptive survey research design in gathering data. Influence of human resource management practices of principals on school administration questionnaire (IHRMPPSAQ) was used as instrument for data collection. The sample comprised 673 school administrators across 32 secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This is made up of 96 respondents for the principal category and 577 respondents for the non-principal category. Statistical mean was used to analyse and answer the research questions while t-test was adopted for analysis and testing of the null hypotheses at 0.05% level of significance. Findings revealed that human resource management practices, such as motivational rewards of principals have influence on school administration. It was therefore recommended among others that the education ministry should give topmost priority to training of principals on rewards and compensation administration in addition to the reward practices the principals are familiar with.

Keywords: Motivation, Reward practices, Principals, School administration.

Introduction

Education is one of the tools for promoting and acquiring of information, knowledge, skills, attitude and values needed to enhance economic, social, political and even technological interconnectedness within and across borders. An important goal of any education institution secondary education inclusive is to enrich and develop one's potentials to positively connect within the society and promote nation building (Orji et al., 2016). In pursuance of this goal, it is the duty of principals as the chief executive of secondary schools to coordinate and control the available limited resources in the school (Nakpodia, 2020). The utilization of

Correspondence to: Patricia Nguwasen Mando, e-mail: patricamando@gmail.com

Copyright: © 2024 The authors. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. e/ISSN: 3027-060X.

How to Cite: Mando et al., (2024). Effect of Motivational Reward Practices on Principals Administration of Public Schools in Makurdi, Scholar J, 2(10). DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14054227

the available human resource to some extent is associated with the human resource management practices adopted for the principals.

The management of human assets has become a major challenge for modern organizations including educational institutions (Orji et al., 2016). While operating managers (school administrators) deal with these challenges on a day-to-day basis, they also play a great role in human resource management (Pitan, 2022). In times past, the human resource manager in an organization had less responsibility: he helped the organization to recruit people and assumed responsibility for managing the benefits program. Today, firms have expanded this role to include areas such as employment screening, affirmative-action compliance, training, development, health and safety maintenance, and contract negotiation and administration. Thus, human resource management is the process by which organizations ensure the effective use of their employees in the pursuit of both organizational and individual goals (Okoro & Ibara, 2020; Surbhi, 2022).

The need for effective operations schools cannot be over-emphasized. Rewarding the employees, especially in a positive way goes a long way to aid the organization in actualizing its targets. This is because rewarding an employee for job well done, propels him to aim more and do more to improve his performance in the organization. Orji et al. (2016) revealed that the ways good reward management helps to improve performance in any organization are attraction and retaining of the top talent, contributes to organization culture, employee value proposition, contributes to employee wellbeing, enhances productivity, engenders and promotes reputation of the organization, improves performance management system, ensures loyalty, it boosts employee's morale, it offers opportunity for feedback, and encourages a long-term outlook from employees (Surbhi, 2022).

School improvement which revolves around positive and proper management of human resources in the schools. There seems to be deficiencies in principals' management of the limited human resources in the school. This is evident in lateness, absenteeism, and other misconduct among staff. The seemingly lapse in human resources management appears to result to low commitment and dedication of members of staff, which could culminate in administrative collapse, if proper intervention is not done by applying relevant human resource management practices by principals for enhancing school administration. The above problem impelled this study to assess the effect of motivational reward practices on principals' administration of public schools in Makurdi.

Theoretical Framework

Theory Y

McGregor (1960) formulated Theory Y as a human motivation and management theory is based on the assumptions that efforts in work by employees are as natural as work and play; employees are self-motivated and take responsibilities towards fulfilling organizational goals; employees are able to apply self-control and self-direction in the pursuit of organizational objectives without being threatened with punishment; employees' commitment to organizational objectives depend on rewards associated with their achievement; employees have the capacity to use a high degree of imagination, ingenuity and creativity in solving organizational problems, and that the intellectual potential of the average employee can further be optimized.

The theory Y is considered the basis of good and participative management style, in which power is de-centralised and the subordinate employees are given true sense of belonging by permitting them to participate in making decisions that affect their wellbeing and productivity in the organisation. The theory Y emphasizes a more liberal approach to managing the human resource in pursuit of administrative goals. The theory also lays emphasis on welfare of employees by ensuring that they feel valued for their contributions in the organization. It is believed that organisations which employ the ideas of theory Y,

facilitate the innovative and creative potentials of the employees for improved productivity. Organizations which are based on the principles of theory Y consider employees as partners, and invaluable assets whose ideas are welcomed for sustainable growth and development of the organization. The organizations based on this theory value and encourage adequate participation of employees at all levels.

In relation to the foregoing, school management that embrace the principles of theory Y, tend to parade highly motivated and committed teachers who are productive. Principals in such schools are usually encouraged to develop expertise for improvement and make suggestions on how best to encourage them to remain productive. In the course of deploying the participatory decision making practices, the teacher is considered as a resourceful and indispensable partner. The principals in theory Y based schools, are considered sensitive and dedicated to their responsibilities, hence the adoption of management style that shows they are prestigious, valued and loved. This way of managing the teacher who is an important human resource in the school, ensures they contribute more, in pursuit of school's goals.

McGregor's Theory Y is relevant to the current study. This is because the theory provided the ideas on how to harmoniously manage employees to achieve the best performance that will favour the school system. The theory made it clear that employee-friendly management practices remain recommended for organisations that are aiming to be the best in their endeavours. In relation to current study, it is expected that the study will borrow ideas of theory Y in explaining the nature of relationship existing between human resource management practices and school administration in Makurdi, Benue state.

Research Questions

This study is guided by the research question:

1. How do motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA?

Hypotheses

The null hypothesis guiding the study was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in mean ratings of principal category and non-principal category on how motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA

Research Method

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. Brito and Oliveira (2016) explained descriptive research as one which involves eliciting responses from a relatively large number of respondents by administering pertinent instruments for collecting primary data on a portion of the population known as sample. One instrument was used to collect data from 673 school administrators across 32 secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This is made up of 96 respondents for the principal category and 577 respondents for the non-principal category (Benue State Ministry of Education, 2023). The instrument was influence of human resource management practices of principals on school administration questionnaire (IHRMPPSAQ). Simple Mean was used to analyse and answer the research questions, and t-test was adopted for analysis and testing of the null hypotheses at 0.05% level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: How do motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA?

Table 1. Mean rating of principal category and non-principal category on the motivational reward practices of principals that influence the administration of public secondary schools.

S/N	Items	Principal category (n=71)	Remark	Non-Principal Category (n=429)	Remark
		Mean		Mean	
1.	Timely approval of salaries of teachers	2.78	Agree	2.88	Agree
2.	Recommendation of external examination performance bonus	2.67	Agree	2.68	Agree
3.	Timely approval of transport fare for attending trainings	2.70	Agree	2.59	Agree
4.	Prompt reimbursement of teachers for money spent on behalf of the school	2.89	Agree	2.79	Agree
5.	Recommendation of high performing teachers for awards	2.56	Agree	2.89	Agree
6.	Recommendation of outstanding staff for promotion	2.91	Agree	3.02	Agree
7.	Issuing end-of- the-year bonuses to teachers from PTA support	2.60	Agree	2.53	Agree
8.	Regularly praising outstanding staff during staff meetings	2.62	Agree	2.66	Agree
9.	Issuing of commendation letters to dedicated staff	2.57	Agree	2.78	Agree
10.	Applauding high performing teachers during school assembly	2.80	Agree	2.56	Agree
	Cluster Mean	2.71		2.74	

Table 1 revealed that mean ratings from principal category and non-principal on each item is greater than or equal 2.50 being the cut-off or point of acceptance or rejection of any suggested practice. The cluster/grand means of 2.71 for principal category rating and 2.74 for non-principal category rating is also an affirmation that all the suggested motivational reward practices were consented to by the respondents. This implies that motivational reward practices of principals do influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in mean ratings of principal category and non-principal category on how motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA.

Table 2. t-test for mean ratings of principal category and non-principal category on how motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA.

Variables	N	X	SD	t-crit	t-cal	DF	∞	Remark
Principals' category	71	2.71	1.02	1.96	0.37	498	0.05	Not rejected
Non-principal category	429	2.74	1.08					

On Table 2, it was revealed that t-crit is 1.96 while t-cal is 0.37 at 498 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. The result shows that t-crit (1.96) is greater than t-cal (0.37), leading to the null hypothesis not being rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in mean ratings of principal category and non-principal category on how motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA.

Discussion of Findings

The study reported that the motivational reward practices of principals that influence the administration of public secondary schools are: timely approval of salaries of teachers; recommendation of external examination performance bonus; timely approval of transport fare for attending trainings; prompt reimbursement of teachers for money spent on behalf of the school; recommendation of high performing teachers for awards; recommendation of outstanding staff for promotion; issuing end-of-the-year bonuses to teachers from PTA support; regularly praising outstanding staff during staff meetings; issuing of commendation letters to dedicated staff and applauding high performing teachers during school assembly. Still on motivational reward practices, the study reported that there is no significant difference in mean ratings of principal category and non-principal category on how motivational reward practices of principals influence administration of public secondary schools in Makurdi LGA. Similarly, Marcel et al. (2020) who examined the effect of human resource management practices on employees' turnover intention in public secondary schools in Adamawa State, reported that compensation and reward system has negative and no significant effect on employees' turnover, even though the current study did not point out whether or not the influence is positive or negative.

Conclusion

Effect of motivational reward practices on principals' administration of public schools in Makurdi is presented. From the results, the study concludes that human resource management practices of principals have influence on school administration. Specifically, such practices of motivational rewards, have influence on school administration. The perceptions of principal category and non-principal category of the respondents with regard to how practices of motivational rewards influence school administration did not differ. Based on these findings, it was therefore recommended among others that the Ministry of Education should give topmost priority to training of principals on rewards and compensation administration in addition to the reward practices the principals are familiar with. This will consolidate on the positive relationship already established between their reward practices and school administration.

References

Benue State Ministry of Education, 2023, <https://www.moe.be.gov.ng/schools>)

- Brito, R. P. & Oliveira, O. B. (2016). The Relationship between human resource management and organizational performance. *Competitive advantage and financial performance. Brazilian Business review*, 13(3), 90 –110. Retrieved on October 16, 2022 from <http://dx.doi.org/10.15728/bbr.2016.13.3.5>.
- Marcel, D. et al. (2020). Human resource management practices and employees' turnover intention in public secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Lapai Journal of Management Science (LAJOMAS)*, 9(1), 153-169.
- McGregor, D. (1960). Theory X and Theory Y. *Organization Theory*, 358(374), 5. Panait, C. A. (2020). Study of employee motivation in organizations. *Global Economic Journal*, 10(1), 1-10.
- Nakpodia, E. D. (2020). Human resource management in school administration in Delta State Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 23(3), 179-187. DOI:10.1080/09718923.2010.11892827
- Okoro, S. E. & Ibara, C. E. (2020). Human resource management in secondary education: Issues and challenges. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 13(3), 465.
- Orji, F. O., Eneasator, G. O. & Nwaka, G. N (2016). The place of information and communications technology in the administration of Colleges of Education in South-eastern Nigeria: Implications for educational administration. *Journal of Educational Studies and Research*, 8(2), 1-14.
- Pitan, O. S. (2022). Human resource development and academic staff performance in Anambra State University. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 3(5), 748-752.
- Surbhi, S. (2022). *Difference between personnel management and human resource management*. Retrieved October 16, 2022 from <https://keydifferences.com/difference-between-personnel-management-and-human-resource-management.html>.

Publisher's Note Scholar J remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.